

Recent Trends in Banking

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Abstract

The E-Banking is an application that has been developed for a well-established regional bank operating primarily in south India. In the world of this competitive environment and technological development, the bank has been computerized in the last four years, and to increase its customer bank has started planning for a concept called as e-banking; with this concept, the bank wants to move very nearer to the customers and increase its basic operational strategies. Through E-Banking the bank wants to introduce the core concept of IT-based Enabled Services (ITES). The E-Banking services are executed only upon the customer, and these e-banking services would fully integrate with the core banking solution that is already in usage. The major idea is to provide a series of services to the customer through the internet and make the customer feel flexible in calling out simple tasks faster instead of visiting the bank every time. The customer is privileged to use most of the system only as a viewing phase, the only online transactions the customer can do are cheque book requisition and fund transfer among his accounts.

Introduction

E-Banking is an electronic payment system that enables customers of a financial institution to conduct financial transactions on a website operated by the institution, such as a retail bank, virtual bank, credit union or building society. E-banking is also referred to as internet banking, online banking, virtual banking and by other terms. Online banking-banking is an umbrella term for the process by which a customer may perform banking transactions electronically without visiting a brick-and-mortar institution. It is the practice of making bank transactions or paying bills via the Internet.

Features of E - Banking

The common features of e-banking include

- A bank customer can perform non-transactional tasks through online banking, including viewing account balances, viewing recent transactions, downloading bank statements, viewing images of cheques, ordering checkbooks and downloading applications for banking, e-banking and so on.
- Bank customers can transact banking tasks through online banking, including funds transfers between the customer's bank accounts, paying third parties including bill payments and third party fund transfers, investment purchase or loan applications transactions such as repayments, credit card applications and make bill payments.

Types of E-Banking

Core Banking Solution (CBS)

Core Banking Solution is a banking service provided by a group of networked bank branches where customers can access their bank account and perform basic transactions from any of the member branch offices. Core banking is associated with retail banking and many banks treat the retail customers as their core banking customers. Core banking basic depositing and lending of money. Normal core banking functions include transaction accounts, loans, mortgages and payments. Banks make these services available across multiple channels like ATMs, Internet banking, Mobile banking and branches. The core banking services use heavily computer and network technology to allow a bank to centralize its record keeping and allow access from any location.

ATM Banking

An ATM is an electronic computerized tele communication device that allows a financial institution's customers to directly use a secure method of communication to access their bank accounts, directly or make cash withdrawals and check their account balances without the need for a human bank teller.

Digital Wallet

A digital wallet refers to an electronic device that allows an individual to make electronic transactions. This can include purchasing items on hand with a computer or using a smartphone to purchase something at a store. Individuals also use e-wallet for mobile recharge and make taxi payments. These wallets have discounts and cash back points to attract customers. To use e-wallet, the app must be installed. The top digital wallets in India are Airtel money, ICICI pockets, JioMoney, Juspay, Money on Mobile, Ola Money, PayMate, Paytm, State Bank Buddy, Oxygen, Vodafone m-paise, Freecharge and obikwik wallet.

Digital Cash

Digital Cash acts much like real cash, except that it's not paper. Money in the bank account is converted to a digital code. This digital code may then be stored on a microchip, a pocket card, or on the hard drive of the computer. The concept of privacy is the driving force behind the digital cash. The user of digital cash issued anonymous transaction by any vendor who accepts it. The special and account code can be used over the internet or at any participating merchant to purchase an item. Everybody involved in the transaction, from the bank to the user to the vendor, agree to recognize the worth of the transaction and thus create his new form of exchange.

KIOSK Banking

This is the latest development on the remote banking front, also known as 'Touch-Screen' banking. A kiosk is a self-service banking terminal that can be operated with both credit and debit cards. The Debit and credit card can be swiped as against the card reader at the kiosk and account accessed after entering the ATM PIN. Unlike an ATM, which is primarily used for cash transactions like withdrawals, deposits and so on a kiosk is primarily used for non-cash transactions like cheque book request, printing bank account statements, funds transfer and so on.

NEFT

National Electronic Funds Transfer (NEFT) is an electronic fund transfer system, which facilitates transfer of funds to other bank accounts across the country. This is simple, secure, safe, fastest and cost-effectively to transfer funds especially for Retail remittances. The money will be credited

to the beneficiary's account on the same day or at the most next day in case the message sent during the last batch of settlement.

RTGS

Real Time Gross Settlement (RTGS) is an electronic form of funds transfer where transmission takes place on a real-time basis. In India, transfer funds with RTGS are done right value transactions, the minimum amount being Rs 2 lakhs. The beneficiary account receives funds transferred, on an real time basis. The customer initiating the funds transfer through RTGS has to have the Indian Financial System Code (IFSC) of the beneficiary's bank, along with the name of the beneficiary, account number and name of the bank. The bank branches, both at the initiating and receiving, have to be RTGS-enabled for the transaction processed. Customers with internet banking accounts can do RTGS transactions on their own.

IMPS

Using Immediate Payment Service (IMPS), a relatively new service, users can transfer money immediately from one account to another account, within the same bank or accounts across the banks. Similar to NEFT, their is a minimum amount for transactions, but the maximum amount possible is Rs 5 lakhs. Users can carry out Person to Person (P2P), Person to Account (P2A) and Person to Merchant (P2M) transactions from their mobile, Internet or ATM. One of the advantages of IMPS transaction is that it is available 24X7 and even on holidays. This can be payments for utility bills, mobile recharge, credit card bills, grocery bills, travel ticketing, online shopping and even educational institutes fee payments through this channel.

Mobile Banking

Mobile banking is the act of doing financial transactions on a mobile device such as smart phone and tablet. Mobile banking is usually available on a 24 hours basis. Transactions through Mobile banking may include obtaining account balances and lists of latest transactions, electronic payments and funds transfers between customers or another's accounts. Mobile banking reduces the cost of handling transactions by reducing the need for customers to visit the bank branch for non-cash withdrawals or deposits.

Smart Card

A smart card, typically a type of chip card, is a plastic card that contains an embedded computer chip- either a memory or micro-processor type that stores and transacts data. This data is usually associated with either value, information, or both and is stored and processed within the card's chip. The card data is transacted via a reader that is part of a computing system. Systems that are enhanced with smart cards are in use today throughout several key applications, including healthcare, banking, entertainment, and transportation. All applications can benefit from the added features and security that smart cards provide.

Green Channel Counter

Green Channel Counter is an innovative step towards paperless 'Green Banking' for deposit, withdrawal and funds transfers within the bank. The customer need not fill up any pay-in slip or withdrawing money from their accounts. The customer should bring his or her ATM debit card and remember his or PIN. The facility give customers ease and comfort in transacting business. This is also an endeavor to offer ease of transactions to senior citizens, especially on a large number of pension account holders who still preferred branch banking.

Demat Service

Dematerialization is the process of converting physical, financial instruments such as share certificates, mutual fund investments, and bonds into electronic form. A dematerialized account is opened by the investor while registering with an investment broker. The dematerialized number is quoted for all transactions to enable electronic settlements of trades to take place. Every shareholder will have a dematerialized account for the purpose of transacting shares. Access to the dematerialized account requires an internet password and a transaction password. Transfers or purchases of securities can then be initiated. Purchases and sales of securities on the dematerialized account are automatically made once transactions are confirmed and completed.

E -Tax and E -Filing

The taxes can be paid online through E-Tax. This facility enables you to pay TDS, Income Tax, Indirect Tax, Corporation Tax, Wealth Tax, Estate duty and Fringe benefits Tax. The process of submitting tax returns over the internet, using tax preparation software that has been pre-approved by the relevant tax authority. The taxpayer can file a tax return from the comfort of home, at any convenient time, once the tax agency begins accepting returns.

Online Demand Draft

A demand draft is a negotiable instrument similar to a bill of exchange. A bank issues a demand draft to a client, directing another bank or one of its branches to pay a certain sum to the specified part. If one has to send money to friends and family or would like to make a payment, the DD can be advanced online whichever is delivered to any beneficiary anywhere in India. The beneficiary will receive the draft normally within five business days.

Advantages of E-Banking Customer's Convenience

Real-time account balances and information are available at the touch of a few buttons. Thus, making banking faster, easier and more efficient.

More Efficient Rates

The lack of significant infrastructure and overhead costs allow direct banks to pay higher interest rates on savings and charge lower mortgage and loan rates. But the rates are much reduced through e-banking.

Services

Banks typically have more robust websites that offer a comprehensive set of features that may not be found on the websites of traditional banks. These include functional budgeting and forecasting tools, financial planning capabilities, investment analysis tools, loan calculators and equity trading platforms. Also, they offer free online bill payments, online tax forms and tax preparation.

Mobility

Internet banking also includes mobile capabilities. New applications are continually being created to expand and improve this capability or smart phones and other mobile devices.

Transfers

Accounts can be automatically funded from a traditional bank account via electronic transfer. Most direct banks offer unlimited transfers at no cost, including those destined for outside financial institutions.

Ease of Use

Online accounts are easy to set up and require no more information than a traditional bank account. Many offer the option of putting the customer's data online or downloading the forms and mailing them in. If the customer runs into a problem, he has the option of calling or e-mailing the bank directly.

Environmental Friendly

Internet banking is also environmentally friendly. Electronic transmissions require no paper, reduce vehicle traffic and are virtually pollution free. They also eliminate the need for buildings and office equipment.

Disadvantages of E-Banking

Bank Relationship

A traditional bank provides the opportunity to develop a personal relationship with that bank. Getting to know the people at the branch can be an advantage when a customer needs a loan or a special service that is not normally offered to the public. The banker also will get to know the customer and his unique needs. But the relationship is not possible through e-banking.

Transaction Issues

Sometimes a face-to-face meeting is required to complete complex transactions and address complicated problems. A traditional bank can host meetings and call in experts to solve a specific issue. Moreover, international transactions may be more difficult with e-banking.

Service Issues

E-Banking may not offer all the comprehensive financial services such as insurance and brokerage accounts that traditional banks offer. Traditional banks sometimes offer special services to loyal customers such as preferred rates and investment advice at no extra charge. Also, routine services such as notarization and bank signature guaranteed are not available online. These services are required for many financial and legal transactions.

Security

Sophisticated encryption software is designed to protect account information but no system is perfect. Accounts may be subject to phishing, hacker attacks, malware and other unauthorized activity. Most banks now make scanned copies of cleared cheques available online which helps to avoid and identify check fraud.

Connectivity

Another issue is that sometimes it becomes difficult to note whether the transaction was successful or not. It may be due to the loss of net connectivity in between, or due to a slow connection, or the bank's server is down.

Conclusion

Today, many banks use internet for their banking operations. These 'Virtual banks' have lower overhead costs than their brick and mortar counterparts. The facility may also enable the customer to order a checkbook, statements, reports loss of credit cards, stop payment on a cheque, advise the change of address and other routine actions. Thus e-banking provides quality services to its customers.

Web Sources

<http://icardwala.com/services.html>

<http://www.infosecawareness.in/online-banking-govtemployee>

<http://www.moneymazics.com/2014/01/demat-account-benefits-of-holding.html>

<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mobile-banking>

<https://sites.google.com/a/muengineers.in/muengineers/computer-project-list/java-projects-list/internet-banking>

<https://www.investopedia.com/articles/pf/11/benefits-and-drawbacks-of-internet-banks.asp>

<https://www.jackhenrybanking.com/new-banks/pages/online-banks.aspx>

<https://www.online.citibank.co.in/citi-nri/order-dd.htm>

<https://www.scribd.com/document/331850915/Introduction-of-E-BANKING>

<https://www.slideshare.net/KoushikHalder4/total-project-report-koushik-58895874>